

Comparative studies on the formation and dissociation of mixed and methane gas hydrates using clay and zeolite

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Abstract

The distribution of coarse-grained sands is one of the most important factors controlling the occurrences and growth of natural gas hydrates. Naturally occurring sediments prominently consists of clay minerals and silica. Zeolites are other micro porous minerals having channels and pores as integral part of their structure. Aim of the present work is to probe the role of synthetic clay, silica and zeolite of grain sizes 44.17, 60.62 and 35.08 nm respectively, on the hydrate formation with mixed gas of (13 mol% C₃H₈ and 87 mol% CH₄) at different weight percentages of additives (1, 5, 10 and 20 wt%). All the experiments were conducted in isochoric method at 6.8 MPa in 100 mL stirred reactor vessel with 500 rpm. We observed that the formation kinetics for clay as additive (10 wt%) improves significantly (~two times), whereas it is comparable in SiO₂ or zeolite. On the other hand, there is no noticeable improvement in the gas consumption. The hydrate formation kinetics in most of the modelling results lead to the conclusion that clay particles act as kinetic inhibitors and promoters at intermediate and final stages which are quite comparable with our results.

Keywords: gas hydrate; dissociation; sediments; phase equilibrium; kinetics

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Introduction

Natural gas hydrate is a clathrate, an inclusion compound, where gas molecules are suspended within a crystalline structure of water molecules (Sloan, 2008). Natural gas hydrates are stable under high pressure and low temperatures. Naturally occurring sediments prominently consists of clay minerals and silica. Zeolites are other porous minerals having channels and pores as integral part of their structure. In general micro porous materials, which can host water molecules in intra- or inter

granular spaces, are known to influence the hydrate formation process by reducing the chemical barrier.

Materials and Methods

Porous sediments with different weight percentages of Clay, SiO₂ and Zeolite were used in the study. The sediments were supplied by intelligent materials Pvt. Ltd. (Nano shell). The samples were dried (at 120-150°C for 6-8 hr) to remove the pore waters. The required amount of the sediment was measured by using Metler Toledo (AB104-S) accurate analytical balance. The main part of the

apparatus is an SS-316 cylindrical vessel, which can withstand the pressures up to 10 MPa and volume of the vessel is 100 mL. A stirrer with variable speed was installed in the vessel to agitate the fluids. The top stirrer was kept-on at 500 rpm for the experiments in stirred reactor for the entire duration (~18 hrs). Cold fluid (water + glycol mixture) was circulated around the vessel with the help of Lab Companion (RW-0525G) circulator, to maintain the temperature inside at a desired level. A platinum resistance thermometer (Pt 100) is inserted into the vessel to measure the temperature with an accuracy of ± 0.2 K. The pressure in the vessel was measured with a WIKA pressure transducer (WIKA, type A-10 for pressure range 0 to 16 MPa).

The cell was then pressurised with methane gas to a desired level using Teledyne ISCO Syringe pump (Model-100DX). After obtaining temperature and pressure stability (far above the hydrate formation region), then the valve inline connecting the vessel

and the ISCO pump was closed. Subsequently, temperature was slowly decreased to form hydrate formation in the vessel was detected by pressure drop. The experiments were carried in isochoric process. Once the hydrate formation was completed, then the temperature was increased in steps just above the hydrate-forming region, hydrate crystals partially dissociate, thereby substantially increasing the pressure. Consequently, as the temperature is increased further the system reaches to a point at which the slope of pressure-temperature data plot changes sharply was considered to be the point at which all hydrate crystals have dissociated. In this way, a pressure temperature diagram was obtained for each experimental run, from which we determined the hydrate formation and dissociation pattern. The pressure and temperature were recorded at each 60 sec interval using the data acquisition system (Chari et al., 2013).

Fig. 1a and 1b. Kinetics and consumption graphs of mixed hydrates

Results and Discussion

Porous media significantly influence the rate of hydrate formation by reducing the chemical barrier (Cha et al., 1998; Yan, 2005). From the literature survey, stirred suspensions would have a greater gas

to liquid surface area contact, thereby increasing the rate of the hydrate crystallization process (Chari et al., 2013). They also ensure the hydrate formation more uniformly in the reactor than a fixed bed, which could result in localized hydrate crystallization.

Finally, stirred suspensions would allow for a continuous production process of hydrates, as compared to a fixed bed which can operate primarily in a batch mode. Lin et al. (2004) and Sun et al. (2003) experimentally showed that an anionic surfactant could play an important role in expediting the formation of methane hydrate (Chari et al., 2013). From our studies of mixed gas hydrates formed by CH₄+C₃H₈ (87% of methane, 13% of propane) as guest molecules, with different additives, we observed a variable change in the formation kinetics

of gas hydrate which is favourable for gas hydrate in the storage and transportation applications. Sloan (2008) and yang et al. (2010), has reported that there is a dramatic decrease in hydrate pressure with the addition of small amount of propane in the methane gas which is caused by the structure change, from SI to SII. Thus the addition of a small amount of hydrocarbon with larger molecular weight (e.g. propane) in methane gas has a dramatic effect on the hydrate formation pressure (Handa, 1994; Yang et al., 2010).

Fig. 2. Comparison of methane hydrates using different additives

We observed that the formation kinetics for clay as additive (10 wt%) improves significantly (~two times), whereas it is comparable in SiO₂ or zeolite. on addition of additives like zeolite (10 wt%) to the water and mixed gas, gas consumption has been increased by 8-10% in comparison with the pure, because of the adhesion of the gas to the

Nanoparticles (Sung-Seek et al., 2010). In our experiments, the zeolite particles however, in nano size had a positive effect on gas hydrate formation, they also can greatly enhance the hydrate yield because of the porosity in their frame work of silicon and aluminium. The dissociation points of methane and mixed gas hydrates at different weight % is as

shown in the figure 3. It indicates that the phase equilibrium points compared to SI phase boundary curve, are shifting to higher temperatures shows an evidence that are behaving like good thermodynamic

promoters. Compared to other sediments, when the hydrate was synthesized at 10 wt% (3 g) of clay, the formation kinetics is fast in mixed hydrates which is shown in the figure 4.

Fig. 3. Kinetics graphs of mixed hydrates

Conclusion

The experimental data for the hydrate yield are in good agreement with the data in literature when we use different additives. Even though, there is no noticeable improvement in the gas consumption, the hydrate formation kinetics in most of the modelling results lead to the conclusion that clay particles act as kinetic inhibitors and also as promoters at intermediate and final stages which are quite comparable with our results, which helps in the transportation of gas hydrates.

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References

- Cha SB, Quar H, Wildeman TR, Sloan ED (1988). A third surface effect on hydrate formation. *Journal of Physical Chemistry* 92: 6492-6494.
- Handa YP (1990). Effect of hydrostatic pressure and salinity on the stability of gas hydrates, *J Phys Chem* 94: 6, 2652-2657.
- Lin W, Chen GJ, Sun CY, Guo XQ, Wu ZK, Liang MY, Chen LT, Yang LY (2004). Effect of

- surfactant on the formation and dissociation kinetic behaviour of methane hydrate. *Chemical Engineering Science* 59: 4449-4455.
- Sloan ED, Jr., Koh CA. *Clathrate Hydrates of the Natural Gases*. 3rd Ed. Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press; En Milkov, 2004; Sloan and Koh, 2008.
- Sun Z, Wang R, Ma R, Kaihua G, Fan S (2003). Effect of surfactants and liquid hydrocarbons on gas hydrate formation rate and storage capacity. *International Journal of Energy Research* 27(8): 747-756.
- Sung-Seek Park, Sang-Baek Lee, Nam-Jin Kim (2010). Effect of multi-walled carbon nanotubes on methane hydrate formation. *Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry* 16(4): 551-555.
- Vangala Dhanunjana, Chari Deepala, VSGK Sharma, Pinnelli SR Prasad, Sarabu Ramana Murthy (2013). Methane hydrates formation and dissociation in nano silica suspension.
- Yan LJ, Chen GJ, Pang WX, Liu J (2005). Experimental and modelling study on hydrate formation in wet activated carbon. *Journal of Physical Chemistry* 109: 6025-6030.
- Yang Mingjun, Song Yongchen, LIU Yu, CHEN Yongjun LI, Qing Ping (2010). Thermodynamics and chemical engineering Data. Influence of Pore Size, Salinity and Gas Composition upon the Hydrate Formation Conditions. *Chinese Journal of Chemical Engineering* 18(2) 292-296.